

**Invited
speaker**

Fame: 2

**Upgrade
exploited PhD
student**

You can play an
additional card in
your turn

**Upgrade
Dataverse**

When others publish
on a shared project
of yours, they and
you can draw a card

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Fame: 2

**Upgrade
Funding
company**

You can get 1
patent (Fame 3) for
each pair of non-
shared projects

**Upgrade
Big research
group**

You can publish
2 papers in your
non-shared projects